

Tailored Research Data Management Training for Agricultural Scientists

A Collaboration between FAIRagro and the Research Data Management Service at the University of Kassel

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Abstract

A major challenge in research data management (RDM) training is reaching the target audience in a meaningful and effective way. Many researchers lack the time and the motivation to engage with generic RDM training, as they may perceive it as too abstract or not directly applicable to their needs. This project addressed this gap by designing a demand-driven RDM training series for agricultural scientists at the University of Kassel, in collaboration with FAIRagro (Germany's NFDI consortium for agrosystem sciences). This collaboration combined the local expertise of the RDM Center at University of Kassel with the domain-specific knowledge and national network of FAIRagro, ensuring relevance and accessibility.

Implementation in phases

The training program was implemented in three phases:

1. **Introductory Lectures:** Two sessions (German and English) introduced RDM principles tailored to agricultural challenges, attracting high participation and revealing demand for English-language offerings.
2. **Needs Assessment Survey:** To ensure the training addressed real-world demands, an online survey was conducted among researchers (48 responses) in the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences at the University of Kassel. The survey identified priority topics highlighting key areas where agricultural researchers needed support. The most frequently mentioned topics included:
 - i. how to practically generate and document metadata
 - ii. the workflow of publishing data in a discipline specific repository
 - iii. overview about tools and functions of digital field books
 - iv. best practices for data organization and file naming
3. **Specialized Workshops:** Based on the survey results, two advanced sessions (data documentation and data publication) were developed together with FAIRagro experts, addressing survey-identified needs. These workshops, held in English, expanded the audience to researchers from across Germany, broadening the reach and impact of the initiative.

Participant Feedback and Lessons Learned

Overall, participant feedback confirmed the effectiveness of the approach, with most attendees rating the workshops positively and expressing interest in further training. The introductory workshops were well received, specialized sessions saw fewer but highly engaged participants. However, participants highlighted the need for more hands-on exercises and discipline-specific tools. Additionally, some respondents suggested incorporating exercises that allow participants to work directly with their own data, making the sessions even more applicable. The results indicate a demand for ongoing training, emphasizing both fundamental and advanced RDM topics.

Transferability of the Approach

This project highlights a model that can be adapted for other disciplines and research communities. Key success factors include:

- Discipline-specific content: Using familiar terminology and real-world examples to engage researchers combined with local support and access
- Flexible structure: training model can be adjusted based on participants needs.
- Local-national collaboration: Pairing institutional support with national infrastructure.

Outlook

Based on the positive response, there is strong potential for repeating and expanding this training model. Future directions include:

- Offering additional advanced workshops based on emerging needs
- Expanding the approach to other research institutions and NFDI consortia
- Developing long-term strategies for integrating RDM training into standard academic curricula

By fostering collaborations between local RDM services and national infrastructures, this project serves as a scalable blueprint for enhancing discipline-specific research data management training across disciplines.

Keywords: Discipline-Specific Training, Demand-Driven Education, Cross-Institutional Synergy

Resources

The presentation slides of all training sessions conducted (published soon).

Boße, S.; Jordan, S.; Rey Mazón, E.; Schröder, K. Introduction to Research Data Management in Agricultural Sciences – Workshopslides, 2025, DOI 10.4126/FRL01-006428881

Boße, S.; Jordan, S.; Schneider, G.; Vedder, L. Research Data Management in Agricultural Sciences - Advanced module: Data documentation – Workshopslides, 2025, DOI 10.4126/FRL01-006428850

Boße, S.; Jordan, S.; Rey Mazón, E.; Sahwan, W. Research Data Management in Agricultural Sciences - Advanced module: Data publication – Workshopslides, 2025, DOI 10.4126/FRL01-006426818

Author contributions

Sophie Boße: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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